

The Relationship Between the Armed Forces and Civil Society / State

Artur Victoria

The relationship between the Society and the Armed Forces is two-way path. The military never strictly delimited at any time around the world, which would fit them from the perspective of classical professionalism, but in contrast, military action has always been influenced by culture and national character, for the inspiration received from the people, State, institutions and various corporate organizations.

In short: the Armed Forces have indeed contributed to define the directions of history, culture and nature beyond the limits of their classical purpose.

This contribution, with its qualities and its shortcomings, results not only from military training and psychology but also of the influence exerted on the military by the Society, conditioned by their aspirations, customs, values, satisfactions, anxieties, frustrations, beliefs and living conditions.

This two-way path has centuries and it is a worldwide phenomenon, influenced and adjusted by geopolitical, physiographic, economic, technological, social, cultural and other particularities.

As examples:

Britain's economy, national psychology, and island situation led it to build its excellent navy and a good expeditionary army which, in turn, supported and stimulated British liberal and imperial mercantilist policy in the world.

The French army of the Revolution and Napoleon, reflected the revolutionary outburst of the petty-bourgeois proletarian spirit of France at the time, along with their external deeds, were a strong supporter of internal revolutionary and authoritarian policies.

The German Army, the instrument of the hegemonic pretensions of Prussia and unified Germany, was always a stimulus for both the hegemonic ideal and the internal authoritarian forces until 1945, except for the Weimar hiatus.

The United States developed its navy from the mid-nineteenth century under pressure from the security interests of its international trade, and the navy, thus inspired, on the Society, spreading the imperial-maritime theory reflects today's in 100 years of projection of US power by the sea.

But how do influences flow into the political-social dynamics?

What mechanisms and instruments of reciprocal action regulate the intercommunication between the aspirations and the values, objectives, and norms of conduct of the Society, the State, and their Armed Forces?

What structural and conjectural influences affect this relationship and give it directions?

The answers to these questions have concerned political and social scientists in classical Greece today.

Summarizing them in a scheme open to the various philosophical and ideological positions that spin around the theme.

There are, have always existed and will exist in all political associations (tribal societies, city-states, ancient or modern empires and sovereign, federations, monarchic, oligarchic or republican nation-states), two basic, multifaceted structural systems, dynamics are conditioned by local and contemporary injunctions - the exercise of socio-political influence.

The first group

It is characterized by the flow of social and upward influence is the diffuse interaction of the Society's economic, social, ideological, artistic, recreational, religious, community, cultural, racial, labor, and other interest groups.

In this group, procedures and the relationship between groups themselves and between groups and the State, search for to practice the principles of the logic of understanding.

However this is not always confirmed in reality, which often involves violence and more or fewer procedures, controlling, especially when groups are structured into hierarchical organizations.

This complex, dynamic and flexible system is influenced, at least at the level of the abstract theory, by the classical views of society-state interaction: the view that understands human sociability to be spontaneous and healthy and to result freely from a will.

In general, the State with its institutions, including the military, its laws and behavior, dictated by moral principles transformed it into a consensual law designed to protect the realization of individual interests.

This evidently extreme analysis, which confers on the State the limited role of mediator and representative and intermediary of organizations, has never been fully realized: in practice, the general parameterizes of interest groups establishes the rules of relationship with the State and Its institutions always meant the will,

spontaneous or induced, of the strong or majority sectors, like were the free citizens of Athens or the manipulated mass, and revolutionary support of Jacobin despotism, and the bourgeoisie of nineteenth-century liberal democracy.

The second group

Is the one, in which the flow of political and descending influence predominates, is constituted by the State and its organizations established for the execution of specific purposes.

These include the military, established to provide security and protection to society and the State and to maintain order through the lawful exercise of violence.

The functioning of this system is parameterized by the technical-administrative rationality, which reduces the space for democratic understanding in general and in institutions, where the differences are resolved by the hierarchical bureaucracy.

This is particularly true for the Armed Forces, whose members are subject to homogenizing doctrinal norms and formation, only threatened on the occasion of severe socio-political disruption.

To this second structural system of the exercise of influence corresponds again, at least, at the level of abstract theory, to another extreme view of society-state interaction: one that questions social spontaneity and even democratic choice understood as vulnerable to passions and interests, which would result in disorder and incompetence in public affairs.

The Society is the regulated integration of individuals and groups, and it is up to the State and its institutions - among them, it is worth insisting, to a greater or lesser extent, under the circumstances, the military organize the Society, system the rules, identify goals and act on them with authority.

In general, ideological models intermediate between the two extremes naturally prevail (the Society organizes the State and dictates its conduct x the State organizes the Society and guides its behavior).

Intermediate models

Influenced by structural circumstances. conjuncture and culture, they seek to organize the State and its relations with society by mixing in various dossiers the procedures and instruments of the rule of law and the rule of men, of legitimacy and effectiveness, of democracy (direct and above all representative) and the various types of authoritarianism.

They seek to adjust the mutual influence between the political system and the State apparatus; finally seek to balance the rights against the State and the rights granted by the State and its instruments, including those of military coercion, in a balanced way.

The words "democracy / democratic" and "authoritarianism" used in the text do not refer, therefore, to a unique stereotyped model: there are many models, generally flexible and dynamic between direct and full democracy and absolutist totalitarianism.

Societal influence channelled through the political instruments and mechanisms of the democratic process, it is the interpreter and integrator of the general interest and is able to contribute significantly to the formulation of political matrices from which the institutions structured to administer state power will formulate their programs and policies that will guide its conduct.

Includes this scheme the matrix of conceptual orientation regarding the purposes and employment of the Armed Forces in favour of corporate interests.

When, on the contrary, interests are not integrated. they do not fit or do not go beyond corporate or local and immediate horizons when understanding is hampered by severe societal cleavages (e.g. too poor mass x too rich oligarchies) and religious, ideological, ethnic or political intolerance when - and because of all this - the political mechanisms and instruments lacking national and social representation

Then the influence of the State institutions grows - among them, under certain circumstances, the Armed Forces, which repudiate the fragility of power - in political and political formulations in the exercise of power: conditions grow for the more or less authoritarian, centralizing state, which is credited by its rationalist and technocratic logic to the condition of disciplining tensions and inequalities, as the intermediary of orderly and secure progress.

It is obvious that such a situation confers to the State a virtual power without formal and imposing intervention by the Society and its political representation (if any) over the purposes and employment of the Armed Forces.

In contrast, democratic order usually works well in countries whose satisfied and trouble-free societies prefer the certainty of the participatory legality, which protects their freedoms, to the dubious legitimacy of technocratic bureaucratic efficiency,

The Armed Forces, institutions that practice the ideology of order, are particularly sensitive to the problems referred to, which affect them in their dual condition as institution that legitimate violence used by the State invested with regulating and co-authoring authority and institutions whose members are part of the Society

When the circumstances that favour the democratic order prevail, they tend to be discreetly available for the formal purposes that justify their existence.

However, regardless of the military will, in some appropriate circumstances to the weakening of democratic understanding and the strengthening of the State tend to naturally highlight the Forces, whose hierarchical and bureaucratized bases, organization, armament and ability to reconcile disparities by coercion (always limited and transient capacity) stand out their presence in the game conditioned by such a situation: moreover, they stand out, even more, when the situation is aggravated by the perceived threat to national security whose neutralization may require military action.

Armed Forces / State and Society

The behaviour of the Armed Forces at the core of the State's power and its relations with society - as, indeed, that of the other state institutions - is always "tempered" by the lack of tightness between them and the various interest groups and also the broad and diffuse social class groupings of the Society.

This lack of water tightness intercommunicates with and sometimes integrates the motivations and anises of the two structural systems of socio-political influence and links the military to various societal problems and movements, including those of the social class.

In fact, the military is both members of the forces and members of the corporate base, as citizens with similar anxieties, values, anxieties, difficulties, preferences, and satisfaction to those of all citizens.

They are both members of institutions imbued with the ideology of order and concern for security and defense, and members of societal groups, whether well-defined or diffuse, of interests or social class, sometimes dissatisfied with the current order and likely to change it.

They are both members of institutions that promote the homogenizing formation and doctrinal discipline, and members of a Society more open to diverse influences and speculations.

This "spice" works best in democratic regimes, where the mechanisms of relationship and mutual influence Society-State-Armed Forces work freer and with more tolerance, but even in authoritarian regimes, they are never null.

Military-citizen

Military-citizen duality is a factor that can eventually induce disturbances and fractures in the Armed Forces. Indeed, the formation of the military ensures homogeneity of behaviour to some extent from the conflict between order and the pressures of unfulfilled demands.

Beyond a certain level of inadequate responses, the military ends up dividing itself between continuing respect for order and nonconformity with the status quo.

In this situation, the directions and balance of military action depend on the degree of hierarchical control or, alternatively, the degree of control exercised by other strong leaders that replace the formal hierarchy, both the more difficult the greater the dissatisfaction of the military as citizens and social beings.

The Armed Forces

The Armed Forces, influenced by societal values, sensations, and perspectives, are State institutions and instruments.

Thus, although they must be politically neutral from the perspective of party-ideological pluralism, they are institutions of a political nature, for the State is a political entity and the forces are intended to support it in the implementation or defense of its policies in the service of society.

This condition of political creatures makes the existence, preparation and employment of the Armed Forces fundamentally dependent on the will of the Society manifested through its channels of political influence and the decision of the State to use them as an instrument to defend and secure itself.

To defend and assure the Society, to survive and to impose itself, even in adverse conditions, it depends, finally, on the existence of clear political objectives, without which it is not possible to legitimize the use of force.

Such will and decision are, in fact, indispensable conditions for justifying the Armed Forces; they are the foundation of their role in international relations and internal order.

They are the political basis of the strategic-operational inspiration of military preparation and the training and professional motivation of the military;

This is at least what happens in mature and developed countries, especially in democratic countries, which objectively and transparently discuss this preparation.

If both do not exist because Society and State are apathetic about national defense and have no solidarity and sovereign projects, or because the prevailing conviction is that there is no reason to suppose that security and order could be threatened, one runs the risk of reducing the mystique that supports the Armed Forces, their socio-political neutrality and their internal and society cohesion.

One runs the risk of seeing them transformed into forces whose members are bureaucratized and "politicized," especially the maladjusted professionals, common in

these circumstances that privilege the corporatist dimension over the professional, classical force.

It is noteworthy that the reduction of military mystique happens more easily when, in addition to fleeting and poorly grounded in societal thinking, defense concerns are further alleviated, if not extinguished, by political-strategic association with a great power, defending the protected country.

When the concepts of integrity or national sovereignty lose appeal and consistency - which has happened before in the history of the world and may become somewhat generalized today.

Such a situation makes the Society insensitive to national defense and the Armed Forces, leading, at the same time, to the loss of mutual trust between the Society and the Forces, to the emergence of doubts in the Society as to the Armed Forces "raison d'être" - doubts or even negative convictions - and, driven by the natural corporate instinct of self-defense, to the propensity of military thinking not to recognize Society and the State as the inspiration and guide of military institutions.

All of this naturally results in a certain functional orphan and the consequent propensity to increase corporate military autonomy.

This explains why, since there are no directing stimuli from the State and Society, the Armed Forces, in the exercise of their natural and understandable corporate self-defense, end up having to define their goals and their strategies autonomously, even in democracies!

It is also explained why the weakening of the defense function, traditionally the most important - in some countries, not so much, but even in them, generally admitted as important in official rhetoric -, makes the Armed Forces look for alternative applications, broadening their routine concerns about internal political and social intricacies and emphasizing, beyond what is really necessary, both their para-police action against low-intensity irregular threats, such as their involvement in non-military activities.

The process of professional deterioration sooner or later leads to frustrations that threaten the Armed Forces' institutional health because, at least at the subconscious level, the classical purpose, atavistic in the military mind, continues to exert psychological pressure.

It ends by spoiling healthy dreams and ambitions from the classical military perspective and by inducing the replacement of the spirit of body and objective professional corporatism that serve the military institutions and the country by the abusive corporatism of a classical or personal nature, which uses both. .

It is therefore an illusion to seek to assign to the Armed Forces civil or paramilitary missions, to justify, occupy them and, as those unaware of military psychology think, moving them away from questions of political and social order.

Military preparation and conduct are not abstract; they depend on what is desired of the Armed Forces.

If, in addition to giving no importance to defense matters, civil or paramilitary missions are assigned to the Forces giving them legal protection and prestige, if the Armed Forces are considered, preferably and routinely (they may and temporarily may as such), as coadjutor appendages of social and economic organs and instruments of internal order, the extrapolation to the power bureaucracy runs the risk of being admitted and even desired, in the Forces and in the Society itself.

Under these circumstances, the military is likely to be psychologically more vulnerable to fascination with some aspects of the country's political and administrative life.

Justifiably, it is fair to admit that, as has just been outlined, military behavior cannot but be influenced by the link which the Society proposes and demands from it: external defense or participation in internal life or, of course, an appropriate combination. the situation of each country.

However, this does not mean that classic professionalism is a sure-fire path to internal military abstention.

Abstention, moreover, impossible because the Armed Forces are instruments of the state political entity with functional responsibilities that, even in democratic countries, justify some interference, exceptionally, in the internal order and, routinely, in certain matters of more sensitive impact on national defense: foreign policy, transport and communications infrastructure and technological and industrial development in its strategic security aspects.

In short: professionalism strengthens resistance to the seduction of excessive and hasty involvement in the country's political and social life, but does not prevent fair involvement in force on exceptional occasions; conspicuous example: the action of the German professional army in the Weimar Republic.

Nor does it prevent the abovementioned routine interference in certain matters, which accounts for the generally developmental and modernizing position of the military in the economic, technological and infrastructural realms, even when they are less enthusiastic about evolution in the political and social fields - a position that is often transformed. in support of developments when immobility undermines national defense.

On the other hand, Praetorian, para-policial, and service forces - sometimes really necessary roles do not inexorably mean greater propensity for internal interference.

Indeed, it must be admitted that in countries of diminished national power and inserted in geostrategic scenarios without external threat or subjected to unequivocal and inevitable protective control of greater power, the National Guard and Coast Guard-style, armed and restricted Armed Forces relevant support, may correspond to true national desirability without implying fort and interference in political and administrative life.

In conclusion

The improved insertion of the Armed Forces into the Society-State relationship naturally accompanies the improvement of this relationship.

References

Born, Hans, Mariana Caparini, Karl W. Haltiner and Jürgen Kuhlmann (Eds.) (2006) *CivilMilitary Relations in Europe: Learning from Crisis and Institutional Change*; Geneva Centre for the Democratic Control of Armed Forces (DCAF); Routledge, London etc.; 278p.

Caparini, Marina (2003) *Civil Society and Democratic Oversight of the Security Sector: a Preliminary Investigation*, Geneva Centre for the Democratic Control of Armed Forces (DCAF), Fifth International Security Forum, Zürich, 18p. http://www.dcaf.ch/civsoc/proj_governance.pdf

Caparini, Maria, Philipp Fluri and Ferenc Molnar (Eds.) (2006) *Civil Society and the Security Sector: Concepts and Practices in New Democracies*; Geneva Centre for the Democratic Control of Armed Forces (DCAF); LIT Verlag, Münster, Berlin, Hamburg, London, Wien; 264p.

National Security Policy (2005), *Backgrounder*, Geneva Centre for the Democratic Control of Armed Forces (DCAF), 5p. <http://www.dcaf.ch/publications/kms/details.cfm?lng=en&id=18417&nav1=4>

Parliament's Role in Defence Budgeting (2006), *Backgrounder*, Geneva Centre for the Democratic Control of Armed Forces (DCAF), 7p. <http://www.dcaf.ch/publications/kms/details.cfm?lng=en&id=25263&nav1=4>

Parliamentarian's Role in Defence Procurement (2006), *Backgrounder*, 7p. <http://www.dcaf.ch/publications/kms/details.cfm?lng=en&id=25266&nav1=4>

Parliamentary Committees on Defence and Security (2006), *Backgrounder*, Geneva Centre for the Democratic Control of Armed Forces (DCAF), 5p. <http://www.dcaf.ch/publications/kms/details.cfm?lng=en&id=18419&nav1=4>

Parliamentary Oversight of the Security Sector: Principles, Mechanisms and Practices (2003), *Handbook for Parliamentarians n°5*, Inter-Parliamentary Union (IPU) and the Geneva Centre for the Democratic Control of Armed Forces (DCAF), 195p.

Scholte, Jan Aart (2007) "Global Civil Society – Opportunity or Obstacle for Democracy?" in Development Dialogue, Dag Hammarskjöld Foundation, Uppsala, Sweden, No. 49, November 2007, pp. 15-27